

THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGY IN ENCOURAGING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN TO READ BOOKS

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the discussion of tasks to stimulate the interest of preschool children in reading books, on the basis of a number of experiments and data, the role of psychology in solving this problem is proved.*

Keywords: *preschool child, psychology, methodology, observation, conversation, reading.*

РОЛЬ ПСИХОЛОГИИ В ПООЩРЕНИИ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ К ЧИТАНИЮ КНИГ

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена обсуждению задач по стимулированию интереса дошкольников к чтению книг, на основе ряда экспериментов и данных доказана роль психологии в решении этой проблемы.*

Ключевые слова: *дошкольник, психология, методика, наблюдение, беседа, чтение.*

The pleasure of reading is not lost on many people. How many books do we actually read? How many books do you think we read today? If we look at history, according to others, our ancestors were cattle farmers and farmers. So Alisher Navoi, Abu Ali ibn Sino, Mirza Ulughbek and other ancestors What about our grandfathers?

If it wasn't for their research and love for science at that time, today our descendants would be proud of them and not known to the world because of them. But even in the 21st century, there are no shortage of great and popular writers. For example: Said Ahmad, Otkir Hashimov, Khudoyberdi Tokhtaboyev and others.

But Among them, the writer who impressed me with his works and novels is Said Ahmad. The novel "Silence" belongs to the work of the national writer of Uzbekistan Said Ahmad. The novel is dedicated to the eternal struggle between evil and goodness. It was published for the first time in 1986-1987 in the magazine "Eastern Star".

Gafur Ghulam Publishing House of Literature and Art published 150,000 copies of the work in 1989. However, censorship serving the dictatorship ideology of that time removed a third of the work without notifying the author. As a result, the "disabled" work reached the hands of the students.

For fourteen years, the author tried many times to restore the novel, to fill in the lost places. He revised the novel in accordance with today's requirements and brought it to the attention of readers.

The updated version of the novel was republished in 2008 by the creative publishing house of Uzbekistan in 5,000 copies of 280 pages and in 2016 by the Sano-standard publishing house in a soft cover of 336 pages.

The fate of people such as Talibanzhan, who lived in Africa under the pressure of the leaders and returned home after losing his wife and child, Mirvali, a womanizer who is ready to do anything disgusting for wealth and position, Azizbek, whose father was killed and his mother was taken away by Mirvali, is told. The work perfectly reveals the evils of the stagnation period.

In the novel, the internal dramas of the Shura era, which seemed calm and peaceful on the surface, and the crisis of the regime are shown in all their tension and intensity. Almost all the leading characters in the play have a tragic fate.

The novel is attractive with its simple, “uninhibited” style of expression. Talibjon is the main character. Scientist. A person who lived far from his homeland for many years under the pressure of officials, returned to his home where he was born and grew up after the death of his wife and child, and “buried his happiness in the soil”, according to his mother.

Mirvali is a friend of Taliban. Chairman of the collective farm.

Zainab is Talibjan’s sister.

The old woman is a 90-year-old blind woman, Talibjan’s stepmother.

Azizbek is a young man whose father was killed by Mirvali, and whose mother Mirvali took as his mistress.

The thing that impressed me the most is that Talibjan can never cry. No matter how much pain he has in his heart, he will never tell anyone about it or cry. It is better to read this book once than to describe it many times.

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